

CARBON/GLASS FIBER HYBRID
AND ITS EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The preparation of hybrid construction is becoming more important as it is unlikely that any one fibrous reinforcement will answer all the technical and economical requirements of automotive, aerospace, or other industries. This paper reports that hybrid cloth is a woven fabric with a combination of carbon yarns and glass fiber yarns. A variety of hybrid cloths are prepared for epoxy resin composites. Mechanical properties over tested and evaluated.

INTRODUCTION

Combinations of fibres, referred to as "hybrids", In most cases, carbon fibers improve stiffness and strength of the composite and reduced weight consequently. Glass fibers reduce composite costs and improve impact strength.

This paper reports that hybrid cloth is a woven fabric with combinations of carbon yarns and glass fiber yarns. Carbon fiber content, warp-to-weft ratios and weave constructions can be varied to meet the properties required and to gain a preferable cost/performance ratio.

Curing temperatures and molding pressures of the thermosetting resin systems are important in choosing production methods. In general, a thermosetting resin system comprises a basic resin polymer and its curing agent. When they are combined, the ensuing chemical reaction will cause. The prepregs of carbon fiber and resin must be stored under refrigeration before using. Overage prepregs will not produce good parts. Choosing suitable matrix system can make these hybrid cloths processed as easy as conventional glass fabric processing using either press moulding or hand

Lay-up technique.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Composite processing

Composite laminates were prepared from hybrid cloth with epoxy resin. Simple wet lay-up vacuum bag technique was used.

This resin system is composed of a liquid diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A and 2-methyl imidazole/diethylene glycol. Some properties of the resin casting are given in Table 1. The glass fibers used are E-glass filaments, and the carbon fibers are a middle strength type PAN-based carbon fiber. The properties of the carbon fiber and glass fiber are given in Table 2. The typical construction of hybrid cloth is given in Table 3. The construction of 2 and 3 hybrid cloth are shown in Figure 1 and 2 respectively.

TABLE 1

Properties of Epoxy casting cured with 2-methyl imidazole

Tensile Strength	Tensile modulus	Elongation	Compressive strength	Compressive modulus	Flexural strength	Flexural modulus	Specific gravity	Heat distortion temperature
(MPa)	(GPa)	(%)	(MPa)	(GPa)	(MPa)	(GPa)	(g/ml)	(°C)
67	3	3.7	110	4	134	3	1.25	130

Note: cure cycle 60°C/2 hours; 100°C/2 hours; 140°C/2 hours.

TABLE 2

Properties of the carbon and glass fiber

	Tensile strength	Tensile modulus	Diameter	Elongation	Specific gravity
	(MPa)	(GPa)	(μ)	(%)	(g/ml)
Glass fiber	1300	70	8	2	2.54
Carbon fiber	2100	200	7	1.0	1.75

Note: The surface treatment of glass fibres used by silane coupling agents.

TABLE 3

Construction of carbon/glass fiber hybrid cloth

Designation			0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Yarn	Warp	CF	1000f	3000f	1000f	3000f	1000f	1000f	1000f
		GF	-	E40 1/1	E40 1/2	E40 1/5	E40 1/5	E40 1/2	E40 1/2
	Weft	GF	-	E40 1/1					
Counts (/25mm)	Warp	CF	120	40	60	15	20	35	50
		GF	-	20	30	30	40	70	50
	Weft	GF	-	10	10	20	20	10	10
Width (cm)			45	45	45	45	45	45	45
Thickness (mm)			0.17	0.37	0.19	0.23	0.23	0.20	0.20
Mix ratio (Vol%)	Warp	CF	100	89	70	47	26	42	58
		GF	0	7	26	47	67	54	38
	Weft	GF	0	4	4	6	7	4	4

Figure 1. #2 hybrid cloth

Figure 2. #3 hybrid cloth

Micrographs of the fractured surfaces of sample are shown in Figure 3. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) indicates that the matrix was adhered well to both fibers.

Figure 3. SEM Micrograph of composite, 1000X.

Composite properties

Mechanical properties were tested on composite laminates ranging from all-glass varies to all-carbon.

Tensile modulus

It was well known that tensile modulus of composite laminates in the direction of the fibers can be written as,

$$E = E_c V_c + E_g V_g + E_m V_m \quad (1)$$

Where

V_c = Volume fraction of carbon fiber

V_g = Volume fraction of glass fiber

V_m = Volume fraction of resin matrix

Since the tensile modulus of the matrix is more less than that of the fiber, and it can be ignored, then

$$E = (E_c v_c + E_g v_g) (1 - v_m) \quad (2)$$

Where

v_c = mix ratio of carbon fiber

v_g = mix ratio of glass fiber

The experimental results are shown in Figure 4. It shows that the modulus of composite increase as the carbon content increases, and the rule of mixture can predict the hybrid modulus quite well.

Figure 4. Plot of tensile modulus against fiber volume fraction

Figure 5. Plot of tensile strength against fiber volume fraction.

Tensile strength

The tensile strength of composite laminates can be illustrated in Figure 5. Which is a plot of ultimate tensile strength against carbon fiber mix ratio. From the strain viewpoint, carbon fibers become the weak part of the composites, since the elongation of carbon fibers are only half of the glass fibers. When v_f is less than v_{minimum} , the composite strength is dominated by the glass fibers, while v_f exceeds v_{critical} , the composite gain strength from carbon fibers. There is a minimum strength of the composites when the carbon fiber volume fraction is about 26%, and it could improve strength of the composites when the carbon fiber volume fraction is more than 54%.

We calculate the V_{min} and V_{Cr} as follows. When the carbon fibers breaks, the leaving glass fiber can just sustain the load.

$$(v_c E_c + v_g E_g) \epsilon_c = v_g E_g \epsilon_g \quad (3)$$

From the value given in Table 2. We get $V_{\text{min}}=26\%$. If the hybrid composite strength is equal to all glass fiber composite strength, then

$$[v_c E_c + (1-v_c) E_g] \epsilon_c = E_g \epsilon_g \quad (4)$$

We get $V_{\text{critical}} = 54\%$

FLEXURE

Flexural modulus

The modulus of elasticity in flexure (E^*) is usually tested by 3-points flexural test and may be written as follows,

$$E_{\theta}^* = \frac{PL^3}{48J\delta} \quad (5)$$

Where,

P = maximum load carried by test specimen

L = span

J = moment of inertia

δ = central deflection

But the shear modulus of composite laminates are much lower, the effects of shear must be considered, the central deflection may be written as

$$\delta = \frac{PL^3}{48EJ} + \frac{1.2PL}{4GF} = \frac{PL^3}{48EJ} \left(1 + \frac{1.2Eh^2}{GL^2} \right) \quad (6)$$

According to the testing standard, the height/span ratio (h/L) is 1/16, then

$$E_{\theta} = \frac{PL^3}{48J\delta} / \left(1 + \frac{1.2}{256} \cdot \frac{E}{G} \right) = E_{\theta}^* \left(1 + \frac{1.2}{256} \cdot \frac{E}{G} \right) \quad (7)$$

The experimental results are shown in Figure 6, it close to the theoretical prediction.

Figure 6. Plot of flexural modulus against fiber volume fraction

Flexural strength

The flexural strength is usually higher than the tensile strength. For example, the maximum bending stress of 3-points flexural test occurs only in a small region and this region does not always coincide with the weakest point of the material used. By Zhu Yi-Ling's formula, [3,4] we have

$$\sigma_{Bmax} = \sigma_0 \left[\frac{(1 + \beta) l_0}{L} \right]^{1/\beta} \frac{1 + \beta}{\beta} \quad (8)$$

Where

σ_0 = the tensile strength of the material with gage length

β = shape parameter in the Weibull distribution of fiber strength,

$\beta = 7 \sim 16$.

The experimental results are shown in Figure 7, the flexural strength is similar to tensile strength in hybrid composites.

INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH

The strength of interlaminar shear (short-beam-test) is plotted as a function of the fiber volume fraction, which is shown in Figure 8. The interlaminar shear property remains constant until the carbon fiber volume

Figure 7. Plot of flexural strength against fiber volume fraction is about 60%, then dropped.

Figure 8. Plot of interlaminar shear strength against fiber volume fraction

IMPACT

Charpy specimens (unnotched) were tested. The results are shown in Figure 9. The impact property gradually decrease as the carbon fiber volume increase, and approach to a constant value at the carbon fiber volume fraction is more than 60%.

Figure 9. Plot of impact strength against fiber volume fraction

CONCLUSIONS

1. The rule of mixture can be used to predict the tensile and flexural modulus of elasticity of composites.
2. The minimum strength of the composites exists at the carbon fiber volume ratio is about 26%, and at the carbon fiber volume fraction is more than 54%, it could get strength of the composites which is greater than all-glass composites.
3. Interlaminar shear strength and impact strength should be studied further.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to especially thank Prof. Zhu Yi-Ling for his guidance.

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